

Review

A Scoping Review of STEAM Policies in Europe

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Abstract: The Road-STEAMer Horizon Europe Program examines STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) education policies across Europe, with a specific focus on integrating the arts into traditional STEM disciplines. Through the analysis of open-access repositories, official documents, and stakeholder interviews, this study conducts both a macroanalysis of European policies and a detailed analysis of national initiatives. The research categorizes EU member states into three groups: high-priority countries (Belgium, France, Bulgaria, Finland, and Germany), countries acknowledging the importance of STEAM with partial initiatives, and those in early development stages. Special attention is given to grassroots initiatives. The findings reveal significant variation among member states and affiliated countries, driven by unique national challenges. In many cases, STEM/STEAM programs are closely linked to broader societal issues, such as financial development, digital transition, and social inequalities.

Keywords: arts; education; policy analysis; scoping review; STEM; STEAM

Academic Editors: Foteini Asderaki and Sofia Mastrokourou

Received: 8 May 2025

Revised: 5 June 2025

Accepted: 9 June 2025

Published: 19 June 2025

Citation: Roinioti, E., Cherouvis, S., Filipowicz, S., Addis, A., Chappell, K., & Karpouzis, K. (2025). A Scoping Review of STEAM Policies in Europe. *Education Sciences*, 15(6), 779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15060779>

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1. Introduction

According to the 2025 report by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC)¹, Europe is experiencing a significant shortage of skilled professionals in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields—a challenge that reflects global trends. Compounding this issue is the persistent under-representation of women and marginalized groups within these critical sectors. However, the implications of STEAM education extend well beyond the direct workforce. By integrating arts into STEM, STEAM education offers broad societal benefits, equipping individuals—regardless of their occupation—with essential skills to thrive in an increasingly complex and digital world.

This scoping review, conducted as part of the Road-STEAMer Horizon Program, aims to address these challenges through a dual focus. At the macro-policy level, the primary objective is to map and synthesize European Union initiatives in STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) education, forming the foundation for identifying existing gaps. Besides this, the report examines the evolution of national-level STEAM policies within individual EU member states and affiliated countries. This longitudinal analysis seeks to uncover trends, adaptations, and innovations in policy implementation

over time, offering a nuanced understanding of the progress and challenges at both regional and national levels.

The data presented here is gathered from open-access repositories, official EU and national websites, policy-makers' portals, and the collective expertise of the Road-STEAMer project consortium. Short interviews were also conducted with targeted stakeholders in Poland and Ukraine, using a concise open-ended interview guide. The paper aims to enable clear identification of policy gaps and support the development of targeted recommendations for addressing these gaps; the text is organized into the following key sections:

1. **Introduction:** This section outlines the research questions and policy concepts that frame the analysis. It provides a foundational overview of the primary inquiries and the core policy principles guiding the investigation.
2. **Methodology and policy agenda:** The methodology section details the approaches and techniques employed for data collection and analysis. It offers a thorough explanation of how the landscape of STEAM policies was examined, including the tools and frameworks used to map existing initiatives.
3. **STEAM Education Policy Analysis:** This section presents the findings from the analysis of collected data, highlighting key trends, strengths, and deficiencies in the current policy landscape.
4. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The final section synthesizes the findings, discussing their implications and setting the stage for future research or policy action. It also outlines the anticipated next steps in bridging identified gaps.

The Context of This Work

The project's primary objective is to develop a comprehensive STEAM roadmap for science education within the framework of Horizon Europe. This roadmap represents a strategic vision designed to align the European Union's leading research and innovation funding program with efforts to foster greater interest and participation in STEM fields. Central to this initiative is the integration of artistic methodologies, with a focus on creative thinking and applied arts, as encapsulated in the "A" of STEAM. The consortium's mission is to deliver a roadmap tailored to Europe's needs by emphasizing key strategies.

First, the project seeks to cultivate collaboration and co-creation among diverse stakeholder communities, including those involved in science education, research, innovation, and creativity. This effort involves fostering deep exchanges and dialogues to promote mutual learning, thereby generating robust insights and shared understandings of the opportunities, challenges, and requirements shaping STEAM education.

Second, the initiative adopts a bottom-up approach that foregrounds the practices and autonomy of educators and practitioners. This strategy intentionally moves away from abstract, high-level conceptualizations of STEAM or generic top-down implementation plans, aiming instead to root innovation in the realities of educational practice.

Finally, the roadmap focuses on putting STEAM methodologies into practice by showcasing exemplary cases and best practices. By building stronger connections between open science and open schooling, the project aspires to amplify the role of science education as a critical instrument for addressing Europe's pressing scientific and societal challenges.

In this paper, we use the term STEAM when the arts are integrated and STEM when there is no specific connection to the arts. Our goal, however, is to emphasize the arts as an equally important field of knowledge and skill.

2. Methodology and Policy Agenda

Examining the intersection of policy-making and STEAM education requires addressing key concepts and formulating fundamental research questions to guide the inquiry. The exploration of STEAM education is inherently multidimensional, encompassing a wide range of perspectives. These include policy development, strategic initiatives at both official and semi-official levels, societal implications, issues of inclusivity and representation of marginalized groups, and the challenges posed by labor skills shortages and digital transitions.

In the context of education, the scope of inquiry extends to curriculum design, the implementation of interdisciplinary activities, and strategies for achieving integration across disciplines. The role of the arts and humanities, and their synergy with traditional STEM domains such as mathematics and engineering, is particularly significant. Moreover, the tension between vocational and general education, as discussed by Al Quraan and A Forawi (Al Quraan & Forawi, 2019, p. 85), adds another layer of complexity, emphasizing the need for nuanced approaches to educational reform.

Within the Horizon Europe framework, our project identifies several pressing challenges currently confronting EU member states. Foremost among these is Europe's ongoing skills crisis, marked by employment challenges and a pronounced shortage of qualified professionals in STEAM fields. This skills gap impedes progress in digital and green transitions, further exacerbated by the persistent under-representation of women and marginalized communities in these sectors. Beyond workforce development, STEAM education holds value for all individuals, equipping them with the critical competencies needed to navigate a rapidly evolving, digitized world. Innovative approaches, such as incorporating arts into STEM and promoting out-of-school science activities, enhance engagement, foster soft skills, and prepare individuals to address complex societal issues like the climate crisis. By promoting interdisciplinary methodologies, STEAM education also helps cultivate broader societal appreciation for the arts, fostering adaptability and resilience in the face of future uncertainties.

Europe also faces critical labor shortages in STEAM and ICT sectors, as highlighted in the Employment and Social Developments in Europe 2023² report and findings from the European Commission's Joint Research Center. These shortages are compounded by mismatches between the skills of tertiary graduates and the needs of employers. Challenges include deficiencies in digital skills, gaps in soft skills among graduates, and persistent imbalances in workforce participation by gender, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and disability. Policies such as Action 7 of the European Skills Agenda aim to bridge these gaps by emphasizing STEAM education and prioritizing digital competence among all age groups. However, more is needed to address disparities and align education systems with the demands of a technologically advancing world, especially as the demand for ICT specialists is expected to reach 20 million by 2030. In this context, the STEAM approach's holistic integration of arts and sciences offers a pathway for addressing these challenges while fostering an inclusive and equitable workforce.

Our work approaches STEAM education as the integration of artistic methods and perspectives into traditional STEM disciplines. However, STEAM lacks a universal definition, reflecting the field's complexity and diversity. The project identifies six key criteria for successful STEAM practices: collaboration, interdisciplinary relationships, thinking-making-doing, creativity, real-world connection, and inclusion/personalization/empowerment, all underpinned by a commitment to equity (Chappell & Hetherington, 2024). This principle advocates for active student participation while rejecting traditional hierarchical approaches to education.

Policy-making, in contrast, has historically been defined within narrower boundaries. Thomas Dye's influential definition of policy as "what government chooses to do or not to do" (Dye, 1992) encapsulates a top-down perspective focused on government action and inaction. Although this approach remains relevant, it fails to account for the varying levels of policy enforcement at the governmental or EU levels and the critical contributions of grassroots, bottom-up initiatives. These community-driven efforts often bring unique issues to the forefront of policy agendas, reflecting real-world challenges that top-down approaches may overlook.

The primary objective of our policy analysis is to gather and evaluate information on STEAM education policies at both the EU and national levels. This involves mapping the policy landscape and identifying the priorities that shape current educational strategies. Key research questions include the following:

1. How do the identified challenges intersect with STEAM education and what are the prerequisites for effective integration?
2. To what extent are arts and humanities incorporated into existing national and international policies?
3. How have national governments adopted EU recommendations and directives and what strategies underpin their current policy efforts?

Although the analysis emphasizes top-down policy initiatives, it also acknowledges the critical role of grassroots and practitioner-driven approaches. Educators, community leaders, and other stakeholders provide practical perspectives that address real-life problems, providing valuable information that complements formal policy frameworks. By integrating these diverse points of view, the analysis seeks to create a comprehensive understanding of the role of STEAM education in shaping Europe's future.

2.1. Methodology

This section details the methodological framework employed by the Road-STEAMer project to identify, classify, and analyze policies related to STEAM education. The process was grounded in desk research, using primary and secondary sources, supplemented by insights from the Road-STEAMer consortium and its network. Thematic analysis served as the main method for exploring the data collected, ensuring a systematic approach to extracting key themes and patterns.

The methodology for analyzing EU-level policies focused on compiling detailed information about various legislative instruments and initiatives. With respect to their type, the policies were classified into four types.

- Directives: Legislative acts outlining goals for EU countries, allowing each country to develop its own laws to achieve these goals.
- Recommendations: Non-binding instruments offering guidance without imposing legal obligations.
- Reports: Official reports that analyze and assess the impact of a policy or provide a framework for future interventions.
- Communications: Documents that may include policy evaluations, summaries of action programs, or proposals for future initiatives.

For EU-level policies, the key information collected consisted of the following:

- Name/identifier of the policy text.
- The purpose of the policy, particularly as it relates to STEM or STEAM education.
- Key terms or concepts encoded within the text.
- Specific activities or recommendations tied to the objectives of the policy.
- Relevant timeframes, where applicable.

- Cross-references to related policies to understand interconnections within the legislative ecosystem.

In the context of national policies, our objective was to capture both top-down policy frameworks and significant bottom-up initiatives that impact STEAM education ecosystems. Two primary dimensions guided data collection, namely formal policies and legislation, that is, national STEAM policies that define overarching frameworks for educational practices, and grassroots initiatives, where we highlight notable examples of community-driven actions and informal programs that contribute to the STEAM landscape. The aim was not to provide an exhaustive mapping, but rather to highlight policy initiatives across different countries and examine whether and under what conditions STEAM has been acknowledged as a central approach to national development. However, the impact factor is rarely quantified, as most grassroots initiatives have not undergone a formal evaluation. Evaluating bottom-up initiatives typically requires the participation of universities, centralized national tracking systems, or policy feedback loops, resources that are often lacking. In the case of Road-STEAMer, the experience of the professional network of the curriculum informed the sampling of case studies, which was guided by qualitative criteria such as the periodicity, size and participation levels of events.

Given the diversity of policy environments across EU member states, the analysis accounted for national traditions in policy formulation, acknowledging the inherent variability and limits to generalization.

Following the logic of Comparative Policy Analysis (Cruceanu, 2019) which involves comparing policy strategies and initiatives across regions or countries, national policies were grouped into three categories based on their prioritization of STEAM education. These three categories reflect the extent to which national governments have adopted a clear and consistent roadmap for STEAM integration, in line with EU recommendations.

1. Countries that place a high priority on STEAM education.
2. Nations that acknowledge STEAM education in their policies but lack extensive frameworks.
3. Countries that do not prioritize STEAM education or are in the early stages of developing relevant policies are highlighted.

As a method that evolves with available data and identifies patterns through cross-case comparison, our analysis examines the policy frameworks of European countries using the following criteria: the presence of national policies focused on STEM or STEAM; a clearly defined set of policy objectives or goals; major government-backed programs and initiatives; the specific target groups addressed by the policies; and the degree of alignment between national policies and broader EU macro-policy goals.

A distinctive feature of the Road-STEAMer methodology was its focus on integrating the arts and humanities into traditional STEM domains, aligning with the broader vision of promoting interdisciplinary education. Drawing on an extensive literature review and earlier work (Chappell & Hetherington, 2024), we proposed specific criteria for the successful STEAM adoption, with an emphasis on collaboration, creativity, real-world relevance, and inclusivity. The policy analysis explored whether official documents explicitly referenced STEAM or adhered to the narrower STEM framework. An interpretative approach was then employed to contextualize the discourse on arts in education, particularly its role in fostering interdisciplinarity.

2.2. Challenges and Limitations

Policy analysis traditionally encompasses four core components: (a) identifying the policy's target problem, (b) articulating its principles or objectives, (c) specifying implementation actions, and (d) conducting evaluation. However, within the Road-STEAMer project,

evaluation posed notable challenges due to limited access to policy texts, a general paucity of evaluative data, and the evolving nature of many STEAM policies.

Limited access, on the other hand, was due to several factors, the two most significant being the language barrier and the lack of systematic recording of policy-making by local governments. Particularly regarding the former, many EU countries' policy texts and reports are available only in the local language, making it difficult to overcome language barriers. This challenge was addressed with the help of the Road-STEAMer network—collaborators across the EU guided us through national texts and policies. Targeted, structured interviews with stakeholders—focused on topics such as policy changes over the past three years, potential drawbacks, and issues of policy consistency—provided valuable contextual depth and contributed additional layers of insight to our data.

3. STEAM Education Policy Analysis

3.1. Policy Overview in EU

The “Science Education for Responsible Citizenship” report ([European Commission, 2015](#)) and subsequent European policy documents collectively outline a transformative vision for STEAM education. These documents emphasize the interdisciplinary integration of the arts and humanities within traditional STEM education to address societal challenges and promote inclusivity, creativity, and innovation. The progression of these policy frameworks underscores the evolution of EU priorities, from foundational STEM education to broader STEAM approaches that integrate societal, technological, and equity-driven goals.

More specifically, the report introduced the “Framework for Science Education for Responsible Citizenship,” organized into six key areas:

- Establishing a Learning Continuum for All: Emphasizing lifelong learning pathways to maintain engagement with science and STEAM education.
- Transitioning from STEM to STEAM: Advocating for the inclusion of arts and humanities to enhance creativity and interdisciplinary approaches.
- Quality Teaching: Supporting teacher development through pre-service and in-service training.
- Collaborative Networks: Encouraging partnerships among educational, governmental, and private stakeholders.
- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI): Embedding societal responsibility into education and research practices.
- Strategic Alignment: Ensuring that educational strategies at various governance levels respond to societal and technological needs.

The report highlights the transformative potential of STEAM to promote equity, accessibility, and the inclusion of marginalized groups and positions arts integration as a means to inspire diverse participation, including increased interest among women and under-represented communities in STEM fields.

Building on this, the 2018 Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning ([Schola Europaea, 2018](#)) reflected a significant shift, updating the previous framework to address contemporary challenges such as digital literacy and automation. Key themes included the following:

- Focus on STEAM: Portrayed as both a driver of educational transformation and a tool for societal advancement.
- Integration of Creativity and Computational Expertise: Recognized as essential for sustainable development and inspiring youth, particularly women, to pursue STEM careers.

- **Lifelong Learning and Societal Needs:** Highlighting education's role in equipping individuals to navigate rapidly evolving digital landscapes.

The recommendation marked STEAM as the cornerstone of educational reform, aligning learning with the demands of modern workplaces and social contexts.

In 2020, the European Commission produced a Communication on Skills Development. This communication³ introduced a forward-looking perspective on aligning STEM and STEAM education with labor market needs and lifelong learning. Notable aspects and instruments included the following:

- **Enhancing Transversal and Entrepreneurial Skills:** Linking STEM education with skill development for a dynamic workforce (Action 3).
- **Promoting Excellence and Networks:** Strengthening educational ties through European platforms like SCIENTIX⁴ (Action 7).
- **Universities as STEAM Hubs** (Action 5).
- **Erasmus+ (2021–2027):** Supporting STEAM education to address gender disparities, with a significant focus on women in ICT and engineering.
- **Horizon Europe Program:** Facilitating transnational collaborations and advancing responsible research and innovation.

The report emphasized STEAM as critical for the European Education Area by 2025, with the aim of addressing gender under-representation and skill shortages, particularly in digital and technological domains.

More recently, the Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027) reinforced the vision of inclusivity and accessibility in lifelong STEM education. Action 13, "Women's Participation in STEM", directly addressed gender imbalance in STEM fields through public awareness campaigns (e.g., ESTEM festivals), platforms such as Girls Go Circular to foster community and mentorship, and advocacy for interdisciplinary STEAM approaches to ensure inclusivity. STEAM education was linked to broader societal goals, such as equitable access to technology and fostering a culture of creativity and critical thinking.

Finally, the European Council designated 2023 as the European Year of Skills. Related policy advancements reinforced the transition from STEM to STEAM within an interdisciplinary framework by integrating digital skills to enhance digital literacy and access at all educational levels. Additionally, efforts to promote STEAM as a tool for lifelong learning, adult education, and technological skill development aimed to ensure equitable knowledge access. The directive also emphasized a whole-government approach, highlighting STEAM's central role in addressing digital skill gaps and improving educational inclusivity as policies transition from national to EU levels.

Overall, the evolving EU policy landscape reveals a robust commitment to positioning STEAM education as a driver of societal, technological, and cultural transformation. The integration of arts and humanities is not only an educational enhancement but also a strategic measure for inclusivity, aiming to bridge gender gaps, inspire creativity, and prepare citizens for the complexities of a digital and automated world. The European approach also highlights collaboration, with universities and international partnerships playing pivotal roles in achieving these goals.

3.2. EU Policy in National Contexts

This section examines the integration of STEAM priorities into national policy frameworks across the EU and relevant affiliated countries, highlighting the varying degrees of adoption and implementation. Building on prior analyses, including the Kearney Report (Kearney, 2011), the categorization provides an updated perspective on how EU member states are responding to EU-level recommendations and societal needs. The findings point to an evolving landscape where STEAM education is increasingly embedded within

national strategies, with a notable shift towards long-term commitments. The following categorization focuses on STEAM, where the primary criterion is the degree of integration among science, technology, engineering, and mathematics—with explicit reference to the inclusion of the arts. The use of parentheses in *STEAM* is intentional, signaling practices that acknowledge the role of the arts but have not yet fully implemented or operationalized this integration.

To evaluate the status of STEAM educational policies at the national level, three categories were defined:

Countries Prioritizing STEAM Education: These countries demonstrate sustained and advanced integration of STEAM education into their national policies. Characteristics of this group include the following:

- **Policy Maturity:** National frameworks reflect a clear identification of challenges, coupled with detailed action plans to address them.
- **Long-Term Strategies:** Policies transition from short- and mid-term measures to cohesive strategies that align with broader societal and EU objectives.
- **Continuity and Responsiveness:** Ongoing policy development and implementation showcase adaptability to evolving market and societal demands.

Examples of this category are as follows:

- **Belgium:** Focuses on STEAM to address labor market demands, emphasizing teacher training and curriculum innovation.
- **France:** Embeds STEAM education within its broader educational modernization agenda, linking it to societal challenges such as digital transformation.
- **Bulgaria:** Recent adoption of standalone STEAM strategies as part of national education reforms, reflecting a strong commitment to EU recommendations.
- **Finland:** Recognized for its innovative approach to STEAM education, integrating it within its holistic education system.
- **Germany:** Maintains robust STEAM initiatives that address workforce needs, emphasizing technical and vocational education and training (TVET) as part of its dual system.

Nations Recognizing the Significance of STEAM Education: This category includes countries with emerging or targeted STEAM initiatives, reflecting their recognition of the field's importance but lacking comprehensive, long-term strategies. These countries often implement policies aimed at addressing immediate labor market needs or specific educational gaps; as a result, policies in these countries may focus on pilot programs or region-specific interventions, while the STEAM initiatives tend to have limited scope or duration.

Countries Not Prioritizing STEAM Education or Developing Initiatives: In this group, national strategies for STEAM education are either absent or in nascent stages. Limited data availability and a lack of comprehensive frameworks characterize this category. This is illustrated by minimal emphasis on STEAM in policy agendas, as well as the absence of cohesive strategies, with efforts often confined to isolated or grassroots initiatives. Usually, the challenges for these countries include resource constraints, a limited alignment with EU recommendations, and a lack of actionable policies to address identified challenges.

3.3. STEAM Education as High Priority

Countries such as Belgium, France, Bulgaria, Finland, and Germany serve as exemplars within the EU for their strategic emphasis on STEAM education. These nations display continuity, with a pattern of consistent investment and policy adaptation, policy evolution with a progression from fragmented measures to comprehensive frameworks, and proper

alignment with EU objectives, with policies that resonate with the goals outlined in EU directives, including gender equity, digital literacy, and creativity.

Overall, this analysis reveals a shifting policy landscape, with a growing number of EU countries recognizing STEAM as a pivotal element of their educational strategies. While progress is evident, disparities persist, particularly among nations in the third category. Addressing these gaps will require tailored support, resource sharing, and a stronger emphasis on cross-national collaborations to ensure a balanced and inclusive implementation of STEAM education across the EU.

Belgium has been a front-runner in integrating STEAM into its educational and policy frameworks, initiating its efforts with the STEM Action Plan 2012–2020. This foundational policy introduced a structural approach to enhancing STEM education, addressing systemic issues such as gender disparity, labor market alignment, and the under-representation of disadvantaged groups. Key elements include the following:

- **Comprehensive Objectives:** Making STEM education more attractive by incorporating innovative teaching methods, increasing the number of girls and students from under-represented groups in STEM fields, and improving societal attitudes toward technical professions.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Collaboration across education, government, and business sectors, and establishment of the STEM Platform, comprising experts from diverse domains, who provided dynamic feedback loops for continual improvement.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Tools such as the STEMMonitor, which tracked enrollment trends and outcomes, illustrated the policy's impact, with over 2600 additional students enrolling in STEM-related courses between 2010–2011 and 2019–2020.

While the initial focus was primarily on traditional STEM fields, the plan did acknowledge the arts as a potential integrative element, though it lacked explicit implementation frameworks for STEAM.

Building on the successes and insights from its predecessor, Belgium introduced the STEM Agenda 2030⁵ in 2021. This initiative reflects a more holistic approach, addressing broader societal challenges and sustainable development, enhanced competencies for students, educators, and industry professionals, and gender-specific outreach to inspire girls to pursue STEM careers. It also indicates that STEM remains a national priority, with initiatives extending beyond education to influence research, employment, and everyday life.

Bulgaria's journey toward STEAM prioritization is relatively recent but has been marked by substantial strategic efforts. The country began laying the groundwork during 2013–2014, culminating in the development of a comprehensive STEAM agenda as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (2021–2027)⁶. Key Milestones and Priorities include the following:

1. **The 2022 National Recovery and Resilience Plan:** Central to this plan is the establishment of a national STEM ecosystem, with an emphasis on digital literacy for all age groups, and the creation of innovative STEM centers equipped with modern infrastructure to promote project-based and experiential learning.
2. **Integration of Arts and Creativity:** STEM education is explicitly linked to creativity and digital arts, reflecting the broader goals of STEAM education.
3. **Infrastructure and Capacity Building:** Investments in facilities, labs, and educational resources were planned, so as to modernize the STEM ecosystem, also relating to the digitization of libraries and other learning spaces to enhance accessibility and interactivity.
4. **Targeted Efforts to Address Inequality,** with a special focus on social inclusion, exemplified by initiatives like STEM BUS Bulgaria (2022), which takes STEM learning to

- underserved communities, and on the development of learning pathways and STEM knowledge maps to ensure equity in access and opportunities.
5. Collaboration and Innovation, with platforms such as the Open Data STEM Portal to promote transparency, collaboration, and information sharing, and planned integration with the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) hub in Bulgaria to connect local initiatives with EU-wide networks.
 6. Teacher Professional Development: Change management and professional training programs aiming to empower educators to implement modern STEM pedagogies effectively.

Bulgaria's approach underscores the role of STEM education in addressing economic growth, demographic challenges, and social inequality. Through the systematic integration of creativity, digital tools, and infrastructure upgrades, Bulgaria is positioning itself as a strong advocate for STEAM education within the EU.

Finland positions STEM as a cornerstone of societal well-being, aligning its LUMA (STEM) Strategy (2014–2025)⁷ with global challenges like climate change and digitization. While the strategy incorporates cross-disciplinary connections (e.g., circular economy and social equality), challenges like declining interest in STEM and gender imbalances persist. Their approach is characterized by well-defined strategic objectives, including embedding STEM into society, enhancing teaching quality, and cultivating interest; STEAM integration, where the arts are recognized for fostering STEM enthusiasm; and support measures, such as collaborations with museums to promote communication and interest, highlighting innovative approaches to societal integration.

Germany has a robust MINT (STEM) framework embedded across educational levels, exemplified by the STEM Bildungskette (Li, 2022). Its Dresden resolution⁸ underscores STEM as pivotal to national qualifications with the establishment of experimental projects enabling students to engage with research early, gender inclusivity initiatives like "Go STEM" and "Success with STEM" focusing on reducing the gender gap, and programs like "Code Your Life" using creative tools (e.g., Minecraft), blending arts and technology. This approach effectively demonstrates how sustained governmental support and integrated policies can cultivate STEM talent and reduce societal barriers.

France's STEM initiatives often center on collaborative projects between schools and industries, supported by foundations and ministries⁹. Related policies include "La main à la pâte", which provides teacher training and resources for science projects in classrooms, interdisciplinary pilot colleges, i.e., prototype institutions in rural or priority areas focusing on creative science and technology education, and interdisciplinary programs (EPI) including artistic creation, sustainable development, and ancient cultures, reflecting broad but indirect STEAM integration.

3.4. Nations Acknowledging the Importance of STEAM Education in Their Policies

Several EU nations have prioritized STEAM education through distinct policies and strategies:

- Austria (policy horizon: 2023–2030)¹⁰, aiming to increase STEM graduates and women in technical subjects, focusing on contemporary role models and regional networking for holistic STEM education.
- Romania (2019–2030)¹¹, by introducing transdisciplinary curricula and partnerships with companies for mentorship, and incorporating creative thinking alongside computational skills.
- Denmark (Technology Pact 2018)¹², focusing on equipping citizens for a digital future through academia-business collaboration and establishing creativity as a means for innovation.

- Spain, with programs like “STEM Talent Girl”¹³, aiming to empower women and align with teacher training to boost participation.
- Malta, where science literacy is prioritized alongside STEM education¹⁴, emphasizing real-world problem-solving and interdisciplinary learning.
- Italy, with programs such as “Art and Science across Italy”¹⁵, explicitly merges arts with scientific inquiry, providing an exemplary STEAM model.

These countries illustrate cross-sectoral collaboration and partnerships, creating ecosystems supportive of STEM, focused efforts to address gender disparities in STEM, and integration of arts as a complementary approach to STEM education. However, a systematic and explicit integration of arts into STEM education (STEAM) remains inconsistent, while teacher training and rigid curricula in some nations hinder the adoption of interdisciplinary approaches.

Greece’s centralized education system creates significant barriers to the full integration of STEAM methodologies, despite some promising initiatives like the Skills Labs. The positive outcomes of pilot programs, such as improved creativity and coding performance, demonstrate the potential of STEAM approaches. However, the fragmented and inconsistent implementation reflects a lack of systemic integration. The Skills Labs initiative (Makri, 2023), emphasizing soft and digital skills and aligning with the UN SDGs, stands out as an innovative module. Nevertheless, the dependency on teacher training and curated content might limit scalability unless supported by long-term strategic policies.

Poland’s Laboratories of the Future program showcases how large-scale investments can democratize access to technology across urban and rural schools. With 99% municipal school participation, this initiative demonstrates a high degree of inclusivity, particularly for underserved areas. However, the program also highlights a major challenge common in STEM education—teachers’ insufficient digital competencies. The inclusion of roles like digital coaches is an innovative solution, though its effectiveness will depend on widespread adoption and proper training. Programs such as the Robot League and Mobile Future Labs are engaging and align with experiential learning principles, but the lack of systemic monitoring and reporting limits the assessment of long-term impacts.

Lithuania’s approach through its STEAM Action Plan and subsequent educational priorities underscores both ambition and systemic limitations. While the focus on ICT competencies and teacher professional development is commendable, the high level of curriculum standardization stifles creativity, a crucial element of STEAM. The STEMSchool Label tool (Raudienė et al., 2022) is a valuable resource for evaluating STEM integration, but the lack of continuity in reforms (post-2020) weakens momentum.

Estonia’s strength lies in its alignment with lifelong learning principles, aiming for tailored and experiential learning opportunities. However, STEAM-specific initiatives remain underdeveloped compared to broader educational strategies. The Rocket69 science TV show is an innovative approach to STEM popularization, making science accessible to a wider audience, but deeper systemic integration is necessary for impactful long-term educational outcomes.

The Netherlands exemplifies a decentralized and collaborative model through initiatives like the Technology Pact. Its flexible integration of STEAM across curricular and extracurricular activities—such as project-based learning and partnerships with industries—provides a strong framework for holistic STEAM education. However, the lack of a specific national STEAM policy could potentially lead to disparities in implementation. The emphasis on teacher professional development is crucial, as is the growing trend of aligning education with real-world STEAM applications.

Latvia’s STEM initiatives are driven by labor market demands and international benchmarks (e.g., OECD). The focus on enhancing secondary education and updating

STEM resources since 2008 has yielded measurable improvements. Actions outlined in the National Development Plan 2020, such as fostering creativity and entrepreneurship, offer promising directions. However, limited emphasis on systemic STEAM integration and teacher training poses significant challenges.

A common trend across these countries is that teacher competency appears to be a universal challenge; while countries such as Poland propose specific solutions like digital coaches, these initiatives need robust frameworks and incentives to attract qualified personnel. In addition, countries with centralized systems (e.g., Greece) face rigidity, whereas decentralized systems (e.g., the Netherlands) benefit from adaptability but risk uneven implementation. Finally, many countries rely on pilot programs to showcase STEAM's potential, whereas to maximize impact, governments should transition from pilots to nationwide systemic integration, as seen in Poland's large-scale efforts.

3.5. Countries in the Process of Developing STEAM Initiatives

The Czech Republic, Slovenia, Hungary, and Slovakia represent countries with emerging or limited emphasis on STEAM education policies. Their respective approaches reflect different levels of integration, challenges, and ambitions, showcasing the diversity within EU education systems. Here is a critical analysis of each country's position and potential:

More specifically, the **Czech Republic** demonstrates limited commitment to STEM-specific policies, relying instead on broader educational strategies like the Strategy for Education Policy¹⁶.

The absence of targeted STEM/STEAM goals within this strategy suggests a lack of prioritization, which might hinder the development of future-oriented skills among students. Without a comprehensive policy framework, the reliance on grassroots initiatives or ad hoc programs may result in uneven access to STEM resources across schools and regions.

Potential recommendations for a more successful STEAM policy include the development of a targeted STEM/STEAM strategy aligned with labor market demands and EU innovation goals, encouraging public-private partnerships to enhance access to STEM resources and expertise, and introducing data collection mechanisms to evaluate the impact of STEM-related activities.

Slovenia has recently focused on digital transformation through the Digital Slovenia Strategy 2030¹⁷, emphasizing digital infrastructure and ICT education. While such initiatives do contribute to the technological foundation necessary for STEM education, the omission of explicit STEAM goals indicates a gap in integrating digital literacy with interdisciplinary and creative problem-solving approaches central to STEAM. In this context, a possible next step would be to expand the existing strategy to explicitly include STEM/STEAM education goals, pilot interdisciplinary programs combining digital skills with arts and sciences, and provide teacher training programs emphasizing the integration of STEM and creative disciplines.

In **Slovakia**, STEM education is an emerging priority driven by the efforts of individual teachers rather than systemic policy initiatives. This grassroots approach reflects a reliance on teacher innovation, but also highlights the practical challenges they face, such as resource constraints and a lack of institutional support. Given the experience of other countries, a national STEM/STEAM strategy with input from teachers and stakeholders would be more likely to succeed, in association with funding for school-based STEM initiatives and teacher training, and collaboration between schools, universities, and industry to enhance access to resources and expertise.

Hungary's recent developments in STEM education, including the Teacher of Science and Environment program and compulsory science subjects in high school exams, indi-

cate a strategic focus on strengthening the natural sciences. The government's explicit ambition to increase the proportion of STEM-related higher education enrollments to 50% by 2030 aligns with broader innovation goals, such as increasing R&D expenditures to 3% of GDP. However, the absence of STEAM integration and the separation of arts from STEM subjects reveal an opportunity for further refinement, especially if combined with mitigating the overemphasis on quantitative goals (e.g., increasing STEM enrollments) without ensuring the quality and accessibility of education. For example, a policy may consider integrating arts into STEM curricula to foster creativity and innovation (adopting a STEAM approach), focusing on improving teacher training programs to ensure high-quality STEM education across all levels, and establishing mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the impact of compulsory science requirements on student outcomes.

3.6. Countries Outside EU and STEAM National Policies

The **United Kingdom** has a strong historical foundation in STEM policy, with continuous government support and strategic initiatives aimed at enhancing STEM skills and fostering innovation. However, despite significant advancements in STEM education and innovation policy, the concept of STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) has not been prioritized at the same level.

The Science and Innovation Investment Framework¹⁸ laid the groundwork for long-term policy development, focusing on improving STEM skills to ensure the UK maintained its leadership in science and technology. The Science Forum, established in 2005, created a platform for discussing STEM education and skills, promoting collaborations across various sectors. These initiatives set the stage for a policy landscape that would continue to prioritize STEM education as a cornerstone of national innovation and economic growth. During the same period, the Next Steps document¹⁹, following up on these early efforts, focused on refining key policy points and introducing metrics to evaluate progress. These documents reflect the UK's commitment to developing a robust STEM workforce, which is fundamental to sustaining its scientific and technological leadership.

While STEM policies were well-established, STEAM (which integrates the arts into STEM) gained attention through advocacy groups such as the [Cultural Learning Alliance \(2017\)](#) in 2016. This coalition stressed the importance of the arts in fostering creativity, adaptability, and critical thinking—skills that are essential in the modern workforce. The Alliance suggested that integrating arts into STEM education could create more holistic, innovative, and future-ready learning environments. Further, the Labour Policy Forum in 2016 echoed this sentiment, arguing that STEAM could help address upcoming challenges by fostering critical and creative thinking skills. Despite these advocacy efforts, the government's Science and Technology Framework (2024 update) continues to prioritize STEM without incorporating arts as an essential part of the strategy.

In the years following these advocacy initiatives, the UK government has doubled down on its STEM commitments, especially in relation to inclusivity and diversity. The Science and Technology House of Commons Select Committee's 2022 report on diversity and inclusion in STEM highlighted the importance of diversifying STEM education and employment sectors to ensure the UK's competitiveness on the global stage. Additionally, the UK's Department for Education is focused on addressing the shortage of STEM skills and ensuring equitable access to STEM careers. Plans include increasing participation in STEM fields by 2030, particularly in computing and digital sectors, with an emphasis on mathematics education, AI talent attraction, and the establishment of employer-led Institutes of Technology. However, despite these significant efforts, STEAM remains largely absent from the formal policy frameworks that guide the UK's STEM initiatives.

In contrast, **Ukraine** has made significant strides in aligning its educational policies with current global trends in STEM education, though financial constraints and ongoing military challenges have impeded some of its progress. Ukraine's approach to STEM education is multi-faceted, with initiatives spanning from primary education to research and development. Notable efforts include the Conceptual Principles of Secondary School Reform²⁰, known as "The New Ukrainian School," and the Great Transformation Program "Education 4.0: Ukrainian Sunrise". These initiatives are designed to modernize education in Ukraine by prioritizing STEM education, updating teacher training programs, and improving educational infrastructure.

The "Concept of the Development of STEM Education until 2027" (Buturlina et al., 2021) outlines an ambitious roadmap for strengthening STEM education at all levels, aiming to align Ukraine's educational system with global standards and prepare students for the demands of the future workforce. In this context, the All-Ukrainian Scientific and Methodological Virtual STEM Center and the Model List of Teaching Means and Equipment for STEM Laboratories are examples of how Ukraine is seeking to institutionalize and professionalize STEM education.

Ukraine's national and regional stakeholders, including the Institute of Gifted Child of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine and the Junior Academy of Sciences, play a crucial role in driving STEM education reform. Their efforts are supported by initiatives such as the STEM-Week event, which brings together educators, students, and professionals to exchange knowledge and experiences. However, while these efforts are commendable, the ongoing conflict in Ukraine has led to substantial financial and logistical challenges. Despite these setbacks, stakeholders continue to emphasize the importance of STEM education as a key driver of innovation, economic competitiveness, and sustainable development.

Finally, even though financial constraints resulting from military aggression have impacted the active implementation of the "Education 4.0: Ukrainian Sunrise" program (Shlenova et al., 2025), Ukraine continues to receive international support, particularly in terms of resources and expertise, aimed at advancing its STEM education agenda. These initiatives are seen as vital to ensuring Ukraine can build a knowledge-based economy and develop its human capital in the face of adversity.

4. Discussion

As part of the European Union's evolving education strategy, several EU countries have placed STEAM education at the center of their national policies. These initiatives align with broader EU roadmaps aimed at fostering sustainable digital and green economies, while also highlighting persistent structural challenges within the EU—particularly the need to improve accessibility and increase the participation of women in STEAM fields. Countries such as Belgium, France, Malta, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Finland, and Germany have made STEAM education a priority, understanding its role not just in addressing labor market needs but also in tackling inequalities and preparing students for a future shaped by digitalization and technological advancement. These initiatives often include a comprehensive, government-wide approach that engages various stakeholders, including educational institutions, professional development programs, and societal initiatives; the fact that STEAM is a priority not only for the educational system, but also for all related interested parties, indicates a strong commitment and ensures a continuing investment, at least for the foreseeable future.

Despite the overarching push for STEAM in many EU nations, some countries, such as Malta and Estonia, have focused on initiatives targeting broader audiences. These efforts span primary and secondary education, with initiatives also engaging the general public,

signaling a broad commitment to fostering STEAM-related skills across various sectors of society.

While several EU nations have prioritized educational reforms that integrate STEAM education, extracurricular activities and school curricula enhancements often serve as key mechanisms. In countries like Italy, Romania, Czech Republic, the Netherlands, and Malta, project-based learning and collaborative initiatives involving museums, scientific communities, and academic institutions are common strategies. These approaches typically target primary and secondary education, with a particular focus on supporting teachers through specialized professional development programs.

The policy shift following the COVID-19 pandemic has been significant. Pre-2019 EU policy texts emphasized citizenship competence and values like social cohesion, cultural diversity, and active participation in democratic decision-making. However, post-2019, there has been a marked transition towards accelerating digital transitions and positioning STEAM education as a key driver of societal change. This shift aligns with the growing recognition of education as a platform to address pressing global challenges such as technological advancement, environmental sustainability, and social inequalities. According to Reimers (Reimers, 2021), this shift is reflective of the evolving role of education in addressing the rapidly changing demands of the world.

In cases where the national policies are oriented toward professionals, there is often a clear connection to labor market shortages, with governments aiming to increase the supply of qualified STEAM workers to meet the needs of the economy. This trend is reflective of a broader European-wide understanding that STEAM skills are critical to future economic competitiveness.

Specific Themes

A consistent theme across EU policies is the commitment to addressing social inequalities, particularly regarding the participation of women and girls in STEAM fields. The under-representation of women in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) is a well-documented issue (Korompili & Karpouzis, 2022), and many EU countries have initiated targeted programs to increase female participation in these areas.

Countries like Bulgaria, Finland, Belgium, Germany, France, Spain, Switzerland, the UK, Estonia, and Austria have launched specialized initiatives to support women's participation in STEAM education and careers. These programs include mentorship schemes, scholarships, and outreach activities designed to encourage young girls to pursue STEAM subjects and to help them overcome barriers that may discourage their engagement in these fields.

In the context of arts and humanities in STEAM education, while their role in STEAM has not been explicitly outlined in official EU policy documents, there have been notable national-level initiatives aimed at integrating the arts with STEM education. For example, Italy's "Arts and Science across Italy" program promotes collaboration between scientists and artists, resulting in the creation of artistic works inspired by scientific concepts. This initiative underscores the value of blending creativity and science to foster new ways of thinking and problem-solving.

In the UK, advocates for STEAM emphasize the importance of integrating arts into STEM curricula. By doing so, they argue, schools can help students develop creative thinking skills, which are crucial not only for the arts but for the innovative problem-solving required in the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics fields. Similarly, countries like Denmark, Bulgaria, Belgium, and Finland emphasize the role of art in enhancing STEM education, with a particular focus on cultivating students' creative potential and innovative capacities. For example, Denmark offers STEAM-specific courses in fields like

aquaculture and video game design, where students can explore the intersection of science, technology, and creativity.

This approach is gaining momentum, particularly in senior high schools in countries like Denmark, where programs are designed to nurture creative professionals who can navigate and contribute to the digital and creative economies. The integration of the arts into the STEM curriculum is seen as an essential strategy to prepare students for future industries that require not just technical knowledge but also creativity, innovation, and critical thinking.

5. Conclusions

STEAM education is increasingly recognized across the EU as a key pillar for preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the future. Countries have implemented various strategies based on national needs and policy objectives, ranging from early education reforms to professional development for teachers and STEAM professionals. In many instances, the integration of the arts with STEM has been a strategy to address gender imbalances and foster creative problem-solving skills among students.

The evolution of European policy documents on STEAM education shows a strategic shift towards addressing contemporary challenges in a rapidly changing world, especially in the aftermath of the pandemic. Initiatives beginning with the 2015 “Science Education for Responsible Citizenship” report laid the foundation for a more inclusive and digitally literate society, with a strong emphasis on science education and its role in societal development. However, while these documents have been consistent in promoting STEM education, the explicit integration of arts into STEM (i.e., the transition to STEAM) has been only sporadically referenced, with little action-oriented guidance in the official EU frameworks. This gap in policy underscores a broader question for future development in education: how to systematically integrate the arts and humanities into the traditionally more technical fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

On a national level, various EU countries have adopted diverse strategies to advance STEAM education, tailoring their approaches to specific national contexts and priorities. Countries like Belgium, France, Malta, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Finland, and Germany have placed STEAM education at the heart of their policy agendas, aligning with broader European goals of promoting sustainable digital and green economies. These nations have also prioritized educational reforms, notably in the post-2019 period, with a clear focus on accelerating digital transitions to foster innovation and economic competitiveness.

Despite the common trends toward educational reform, the integration of arts into these initiatives remains relatively fragmented. Social inequalities, especially in terms of gender disparities in STEM fields, have spurred the creation of specialized programs aimed at promoting female participation and ensuring greater inclusivity in STEAM disciplines. However, the specific role of the arts in this context has largely been underdeveloped in EU policy, and is more prevalent in bottom-up initiatives or national projects. In this context, Italy’s “Arts and Science across Italy” initiative, Denmark’s STEAM courses, and the UK’s more bottom-up STEAM approach, supported through the likes of the CLA ([Cultural Learning Alliance, 2017](#)), exemplify national-level efforts to integrate the arts into the broader STEAM framework and emphasize the development of creativity, innovation, and critical thinking, skills that are essential in preparing students for the evolving global economy.

While our review acknowledges that current EU policy and funding efforts prioritize STEAM education as a strategic response to skills shortages, digital transformation, and societal inequalities, we also recognize that this emphasis is not without tensions. The very notion of STEAM was introduced precisely to address the narrow instrumentalism

of traditional STEM by integrating creativity, critical thinking, and cultural awareness. However, as some critics have argued, when the arts and humanities are merely “added on” to an essentially STEM-driven agenda, their potential to reshape educational priorities is limited (Chappell & Hetherington, 2024).

This, essentially, calls for deeper reflection on whether the current focus on STEAM fully addresses the complex social, environmental, and ethical challenges Europe faces. Re-grounding education in culture and humanistic inquiry, rather than simply supplementing STEM with aesthetic elements, may offer alternative and complementary pathways. Future policy work should explore these paradigms more explicitly, including how arts-led or humanities-driven educational models might inform broader educational reform.

In this context, the Road-STEAMer project, with its holistic educational approach, highlights the importance of fostering critical thinking and self-development through interdisciplinary methods. This approach reflects a broader shift in national education policy, where governments are increasingly turning to STEM disciplines as central to addressing societal challenges, such as the ongoing digital transition and the green economy. In this context, by analyzing the national implementations of STEAM programs, we gain crucial insight into how different audiences are being targeted and how policy objectives are being shaped in response to these efforts. This understanding provides a critical foundation for identifying policy gaps at the European level, and proposing policies to tackle them, ensuring that it meets the needs of diverse learners and future-proofing European education for the challenges ahead.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, methodology and formal analysis, E.R. and K.K.; investigation and resources, all authors; data curation, E.R.; writing—original draft preparation, E.R. and K.K.; writing—review and editing, all authors; supervision, K.K.; funding acquisition, all authors. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was supported by the Horizon Europe Road-STEAMer project “Developing a STEAM Roadmap for Science Education in Horizon Europe”, grant number: 101058405.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: No new data were created or analyzed in this study.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
STEAM	Science, Technology, Arts, Engineering, Mathematics
EU	European Union
JRC	Joint Research Centre

Notes

¹ European Education Area, STEM education: report highlights need for more policy efforts and research, published: 22 January 2025, <https://education.ec.europa.eu/news/stem-education-report-highlights-need-for-more-policy-efforts-and-research> (accessed on 1 May 2025).

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